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Comparative Effects Of Maitland And Mulligan Spinal Mobilizations Along With Canal Enlargement Exercises In Patients Of Lumbar Spinal Stenosis

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Canal Enlargement Exercises, Maitland Mobilization, Mulligan Mobilization, Lumbar Spinal Stenosis, NPRS, MODI, SSS

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Background: About 90% of individuals faced the low back pain in their life time and the spinal stenosis of lumbar spine is one the main causes for the radiating symptoms along the chronic low back pain. Stretching, strengthening, traction and electrotherapy were commonly practiced interventions in lumbar stenosis. But spinal mobilization has a great impact on symptoms severity and thus, reducing the disability.

Objective: To compare the effects of Maitland central postero anterior mobilization and Mulligan transverse mobilization along with canal enlargement exercises in patients of lumbar Spinal Stenosis

Methods: A study was randomized control trail that was conducted at Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot. A total of 38 patients meet the inclusion criteria. The patients were assigned to one of the two groups randomly in group A and group B. Both groups received the conventional treatment and canal enlargement exercises. Additionally, Group A received the Maitland central posteroanterior mobilization while Group B received the Mulligan spinal transverse mobilization. Treatment was given for 3 weeks and 4 sessions per week. Outcome measures include the Numeric pain rating scale (NPRS), Modified Oswestry disability index (MODI) and Swiss spinal stenosis score (SSSS) to measure pain, disability and functional activities at the start day and at end of 3rd week of the treatment sessions.

Results: In each group 19 participants were allocated. Both groups have same baseline characteristics i.e. age, BMI, gender distribution. Intragroup comparison using the paired sample t test and Wilcoxon signed-rank Test shows the significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in decreasing pain, disability and improves functional status. Intergroup comparison using the independent sample t test for MODI and SSSS revealed the significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.05$) in reduction of disability and improves the functional activities. Intergroup comparison using the Mann Whitney U test for NPRS shows no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in both groups in reducing the level of pain.

Conclusion: A study concludes that Maitland mobilizations and Mulligan mobilizations, both approaches were similar in their effectiveness in decreasing pain but Maitland mobilization showed more significant difference to alleviate the disability, functional restriction in lumbar spinal stenosis and settle down the symptoms. The findings are favorable regarding the inclusion of Maitland techniques in addition to the canal enlargement exercises to manage LSS completely.

INTRODUCTION:

Given the continuous increase in human life expectancy, it is projected that approximately 90% of individuals will encounter episodes of low back pain during their lifetime (1). Lumbar spinal stenosis is an increasingly prevalent disease characterized by a constriction of the central spinal canal, lateral recess or neural foramina, leading to potential neurological compromise (2). Generally, stenosis is classified as either congenital or acquired, with the acquired variety being the predominant form. It is primarily attributable to degenerative alterations, often age-related which result in the constriction of the spinal canal. This narrowing can give rise to progressively worsening nociceptive symptoms in leg and back, sensory deficits and neuromuscular weakness (3). The clinical manifestations of lumbar spinal stenosis encompass nociceptive pain, paresthesia, hypoesthesia, and motor weakness in the lumbar and lower extremities, which arise due to the compression and entrapment of the lumbosacral nerve roots within the constricted neural canal and foraminal spaces (4).

Magnetic resonance imaging is extensively utilized as a diagnostic modality for the detection of lumbar canal stenosis, owing to its ability to provide detailed soft tissue visualization and precise anatomical assessment due to its exceptional sensitivity and specificity in evaluating the lumbar spine, (2). Several studies conducted consistently support the efficacy of various physiotherapy approaches for managing patients with lumbar canal stenosis. These approaches include manual therapy techniques such as lumbar and neural mobilization, as well as therapeutic methods like massage. Additionally, core conditioning workouts, the application of hydro-collateral packs, water pool therapy, have been found beneficial. Other treatment options, such as ice therapy, acupuncture, flexion exercises and modalities including therapeutic ultrasound and transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation also demonstrate positive outcomes in the lumbar stenosis patients (6).

In this study, we conduct a comparative analysis of Maitland central posteroanterior mobilization vs Mulligan transverse mobilization in conjunction with canal enlargement exercises. A passive, accessory intervertebral movement called Maitland spinal mobilization is designed to address both accessory and physiological motions of the affected lumbar intervertebral segments. Out of the 5 grades, Grade III central posteroanterior mobilization is given for spinal stenosis (2, 7). The patient is positioned in a prone stance, with the head moved to one side and the upper limbs either extended overhead or placed at the patients sideway. The mobilization is applied to the targeted vertebral segments using the ulnar border of the therapist's hand, using hook of the hamate and the pisiform bones. The intervention consists of three sets of oscillatory movements, each lasting 40 seconds, delivered at the maximum depth that is bearable to the patient, with a frequency of 1 to 2 Hz. The overall duration of the central posteroanterior mobilization session spans 8-10 minutes, interspersed with 60 seconds of rest periods between each mobilization cycle (2).

In 1990, Brian Mulligan pioneered a method referred to as spinal mobilizations with limb movements. This technique involves the application of a sustained transverse glide to the spinous process of a vertebra while concurrently performing the restricted movement of the peripheral upper or lower limb, either actively or passively. The primary focus of this approach is that the mobilization should facilitate symptom-free movement. Mulligan asserted that these mobilization techniques are particularly beneficial when the restriction in peripheral joint motion stems from spinal dysfunction (8).

A diagnostic test for the spinal stenosis is the modified kemp test which is also called the Singh-Hartl foraminal compression test. Kemp test is a provocative test to rule out the facet joint issue which is probable chances for having foraminal stenosis. In the modified version, the participant was instructed to carry out lumbar extension combined with rotation on a painful side. Test was considered positive if the patient has pain and radiating symptoms on same side leg were elevated within first 0 to 10 seconds of holding the position (10).

Canal enlargement exercises refer to a targeted set of exercises designed to facilitate an increase in the dimensions of the lateral canal stenosis. These exercises include bilateral knee-to-chest stretches, the lion stretch, cat-camel movements (2, 4) and kneeling with a forward bend, coupled with an arm stretch from the

quadruped position. These therapeutic maneuvers aim to promote spinal mobility and enhance the space within the canals (4).

MATERIAL & METHODS

This study was randomized control trial (single blinded). The trail registration no. is NCT07080073. This study was conducted in the Allama Iqbal memorial teaching hospital, Sialkot. This study was completed within 8 months (September 2024 to April 2025) after synopsis approval. Sample size was calculated through g*power using numeric pain rate scale (4). By considering 10% attrition rate sample size was 38. Group A patients received the Maitland's mobilizations, canal enlargement exercises and conventional treatment. (2, 4) while Group B patients received the Mulligan mobilizations, canal enlargement exercises and conventional treatment. (4). Conventional treatment includes, Hot pack on lumbar spine for approximately 20 mins, TENS across the lumbar spine for 20 mins on biphasic pulse, 2 channels, frequency of 90 Hz, 100ms width. Hamstring stretching 3-15 repetitions increases progressively with weeks with 30 sec holds. Piriformis stretching 3-15 repetitions increases progressively with weeks with 30 sec hold (2). Canal enlargement exercises include, Bilateral knee to chest exercises for 5-10 repetitions with 20 sec holds, LION stretch for 3-5 repetitions with 20 sec holds, Cat and camel exercises for 5-7 repetitions with 10 sec holds. These exercises were practiced four times a week for three weeks (2). In this study non probability convenient sampling method was used. Inclusion Criteria was, Age group between 25-40 years, Both males and females were included (4, 19), Patient with low back pain along with unilateral radiating symptoms (4, 17), Having symptoms from at least 3 months with pain severity not more than 7 on NPRS. Diagnosed case of slipped disc or herniation causing spinal stenosis, confirmed by physical examination and/or MRI (2, 4) Exclusion criteria was Chronic inflammatory or infectious disease, neoplasm, hematological disorders, traumatic vertebral injuries, Spondylitis (2, 17, 19), Any concurrent major disease like renal failure, diabetes, cancer, tumor, Low back pain with bilateral radiating symptoms, Pregnancy, Cognitive alteration and non-co-operative patient (4) and Spinal surgery (2, 17, 19). Data collection tools were Swiss spinal stenosis questionnaire (16, 17), Numeric pain rate scale (4), Modified ODI (4, 19).

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

The data was collected from Allama Iqbal memorial teaching hospital, Sialkot. A total of 47 patients (N= 47) were assessed for the eligibility criteria by using non-probability convenient sampling technique. The demographic data during the initial assessment was collected by the therapist while ensuring the confidentiality. The non-probability convenient sampling techniques was used to recruit the participants. Random allocation to group A (Maitland mobilization with canal enlargement exercises and conventional treatment) or group B (Mulligan mobilization with canal enlargement exercises and conventional treatment) was taken by the sealed opaque envelop method. This study was Single-blinded. Only the patient was blind.

CONSORT 2010 Flow Diagram:

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

The statistical software IBM SPSS Statistics SPSS 25.0 is used for calculations. After assessing the normality by Shapiro-Wilk test, if the p value is greater than 0.05 the data is distributed normally. So parametric test is applied. If p value is less than 0.05 than non-parametric test is applied.

RESULTS

Baseline outcomes revealed that Group A (Maitland) consisted of an average age of 30.89 ± 5.01 years, weight of 70.42 ± 9.99 kg, height of 161.38 ± 7.97 cm, and BMI of 27.19 ± 3.93 kg/m², respectively, with 17 females (89.5%) and 2 males (10.5%). Group B (Mulligan) consisted of an average age of 28.84 ± 6.67 years, weight of 71.53 ± 9.36 kg, height of 161.38 ± 7.22 cm, and BMI of 28.06 ± 3.32 kg/m², respectively, with 17 females (89.5%) and 2 males (10.5%). It was statistically established that all the mentioned characteristics had no significant difference in the baseline ($p > 0.05$ in all comparisons), so both groups were effectively matched prior to intervention.

Figure 1: Histogram of Age of group A participants participants

Figure 2: Histogram of Age of the group B

Figure 3: Histogram of weight in kgs of group A participants

Figure 4: Histogram of weight in kgs of group B participants

Figure 5: Histogram of height in cm of group A participants of group B participants

Figure 6: Histogram of height in cm of group B participants

Figure 7: Histogram of BMI of group A participants participants

Figure 8: Histogram of BMI of group B participants

Figure 9: Bar chart of the gender of group A participants

Figure 10: Bar chart of the gender of group B participants

Table 1: Test of normality

Variable	Group	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic	p-value	Normality
Pre-treatment Modified Oswestry Index	A	0.920	0.113	Normal
	B	0.904	0.057	Normal
Post-treatment Modified Oswestry Index	A	0.903	0.054	Normal
	B	0.915	0.093	Normal
Pre-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	A	0.968	0.744	Normal
	B	0.943	0.304	Normal
Post-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	A	0.931	0.179	Normal
	B	0.910	0.075	Normal
Pre-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	0.808	0.002	Skewed
	B	0.756	0.000	Skewed
Post-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	0.894	0.039	Skewed
	B	0.873	0.016	Skewed

Table 2: Intergroup comparison of Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score and Modified Oswestry Disability Index (Independent sample t-test)

Variable	Group A (Mean ± SD)	Group B (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Pre-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	30.79 ± 3.65	33.11 ± 4.34	0.084
Post-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	17.89 ± 2.18	20.26 ± 2.33	0.003
Pre-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	56.32 ± 5.86	55.79 ± 4.80	0.764
Post-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	30.53 ± 3.39	33.68 ± 3.96	0.012

In terms of Modified Oswestry Disability Index, baseline comparability for both group shows no statistically significant difference in pre-treatment (56.32 ± 5.86 vs. 55.79 ± 4.80 ; $p = 0.764$). But Group A improved considerably more than Group B at the end of treatment (30.53 ± 3.39 vs. 33.68 ± 3.96 ; $p = 0.012$). These findings show that although both groups showed improvement after treatment, Group A outperformed the other group in terms of spinal stenosis and disability scores, with statistically significant differences noted after treatment.

Table 3: Intragroup comparison of Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score and Modified Oswestry Disability Index (Paired sample t-test)

Variable	Group	Mean ± SD	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Pre-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	A	30.79 ± 3.65	12.89	15.336	0.000
Post-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	A	17.89 ± 2.18			
Pre-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	B	33.11 ± 4.34	12.84	13.143	0.000

Post-treatment Swiss Spinal Stenosis Score	B	20.26 ± 2.33			
Pre-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	A	56.32 ± 5.86	25.79	15.870	0.000
Post-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	A	30.53 ± 3.39			
Pre-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	B	55.79 ± 4.80	22.11	12.605	0.000
Post-treatment Modified Oswestry Disability Index	B	33.68 ± 3.96			

According to these results, both treatment groups saw notable post-treatment improvements in pain and disability metrics. Nonetheless, Group A's marginally higher MODI and SSSS score improvement suggested a potentially more successful result.

Table 4: Intergroup comparison of Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Mann-Whitney U Test)

Variable	Group	Median	IQR (25th–75th Percentile)	Mann-Whitney U	Z	p-value
Pre-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	6.0	5.0 – 7.0	174.000	-0.202	0.840
	B	6.0	5.0 – 7.0			
Post-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	3.0	2.0 – 4.0	153.000	-0.847	0.397
	B	3.0	3.0 – 4.0			

These findings imply that Group A and Group B's Numerical Pain Rate Scale scores did not differ significantly at either time point.

Table 5+: Intragroup comparison of Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Wilcoxon Signed- Rank Test)

Variable	Group	Median	IQR (25th–75th Percentile)	Z Value	p-value (2-tailed)
Pre-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	6.0	5.0 – 7.0	-3.769	0.000
Post-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	A	3.0	2.0 – 4.0		
Pre-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	B	6.0	5.0 – 7.0	-3.751	0.000
Post-treatment Numeric Pain Rate Scale	B	3.0	3.0 – 4.0		

These results show that after the intervention, pain levels significantly decreased in both treatment groups.

DISCUSSIONS:

The current research study investigates the effects of Maitland compared to Mulligan spinal mobilization in cases of lumbar spinal stenosis (LSS) by incorporating canal enlargement exercises. As was shown in our results, both interventions had a significant effect, but Maitland mobilization was proven to be more effective to change functional disability and stenosis-specific symptoms than Mulligan mobilization. These techniques proved equally effectual for decreasing the pain.

There was a significant difference in the post treatment SSS scores between Group A (Group A (Maitland mobilization) 17.89 + / 2.18 and Group B (Mulligan mobilization) 20.26 + / 2.33; $p=0.030$). Both proved to have significant within-group improvements, with means of 12.89- and 12.84-point improvement in Maitland and Mulligan groups respectively ($p<0.001$ in both cases). The results are similar with the report by C Gong et al. (2023) that showed better outcomes in stenosis-specific outcomes with oscillatory (Maitland-style) mobilizations with other techniques (13).

The results of our study demonstrated a great overall increase in functionality in Group A (Maitland: 30.53 +/-3.39) versus Group B (Mulligan: 33.68 +/-3.96; $p=0,012$), although the scores were comparable initially (56.32 vs 55.79). These findings can be evidenced by Ibrahim et al. (2023) who showed that Maitland central posteroanterior mobilization could contribute to 28.7 percent increased improvements in the ODI scores than non-specific mobilizations in patients. According to that study, this excellent effect was explained by very accurate segmental impact on particular levels of influence which Maitland proposed (12). The same can be said of a study by Gilbert et al. (2019), who discovered that the utilization of Maitland mobilizations and flexion or stretching exercises (which is similar to our treatment approach) yielded an improved outcome of disability when compared to mobilization itself, further legitimizing our method of treatment (31).

The pain reduction following the present study was equal in both intervention groups, where the median NPRS scores were reduced in the intervention group 6.0-3.0 ($p<0.001$) and there were no intergroup differences ($p=0.397$). These findings correspond to those of Scheinder et al. (2019) who performed a RCT and found meaningful differences in the outcomes of pain association with the use of different manual

therapy methods to treat LSS, all of which had moderate effect size (SMD = 0.6) (16). In a similar fashion, an analogous NPRS decline of around 2.5 points was found in both Maitland and Mulligan strategies in cases involving acute LSS in Yakut et al. (2021), which serves to verify the premise that both methods are equivalent in managing pain levels among LSS patients (14).

Nonetheless, there has been an observation of different findings as shown in some studies. Temporito et al. (2022) found that Mulligan strategies had a significant difference in pain relief after the first 4 weeks of treatment (mean difference 1.2 points) but that these effects became the same after 12 weeks. It alludes to the fact that the two techniques eventually generate the same effect in regard to pain reduction but the technique by Mulligan can be more relieving in certain instances (34).

However, recent studies by Jenses et al. (2021) have demonstrated the differences between the responses to treatment based on the plausible heterogeneity of the LSS subtypes (36). It is imperative to consider the sustainability of treatment effects. Longitudinal research conducted by Burgstaller et al. (2020) observed LSS patients during the year following the intervention and found out that though short time effects were similar in both approaches, the benefits of Maitland method lasted longer (37).

Nevertheless, the Fornari et al. (2020) In an effort to initiate global standards of clinical practice, the World Federation of Neurosurgical Societies Spine Committee hold on to a consensus conference on the conservative management of degenerative lumbar spine stenosis (LSS). Literature reviews were systematically subjected to expert panelists who formulated and voted recommendations of treatment. The resulting consensus affirmed 14 statements, among which are the following: 1) physical therapy of 3 months in minimal-neurologic cases, 2) conservative care should be the treatment of choice in the initial presentations that are uncomplicated; 3) surgery if the symptoms are moderate- severe or acute radicular deficit. Although there was low efficacy with epidural injections, the results of this study differed with that of the committee concerning the durability of treatment (38).

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Maitland mobilizations and Mulligan mobilizations, both approaches were similar in their effectiveness in decreasing pain but Maitland mobilization showed more significant difference to alleviate the disability, functional restriction in lumbar spinal stenosis and settle down the symptoms. The findings are favorable regarding the inclusion of Maitland techniques in addition to the canal enlargement exercises to manage LSS completely.

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